

SPECIFICATION OF EUPHEMISMS, DYSPEMISMS, VULGAR WORDS AND EXPRESSIONS IN THE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY OF SIROJIDDIN ALIKHON ORZU "CHAROGHI KHIDAYAT"

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that those dictionaries are a rare monument that transmits the language and culture of a society from generation to generation. Dictionaries that express a language and its elements are historical and lexicographic works that report on the culture and customs of the worldview of its representatives (ethnography) and are also important because they embody the linguistic cumulative function of language. In this regard, lexicographers in their works explain a specific language, as well as social at present time, linguo-linguistic traditions, language features, as well as history, customs, and mores of peoples in order to illuminate concepts about language. Taboos, euphemisms and dysphemism, morality, behavior, spiritual and psychological, religious and mythological beliefs, in a word, a worldview (mentality) and culture. This is probably why the dictionary and culture of the linguistic wealth and culture of the people in the Persian-Tajik language is called "Farhang" and it will not be a mistake if we suggest that this is the most correct approach.*

Keywords: *taboos, euphemisms and dysphemism, morality, behavior, spiritual and psychological, religious and mythological beliefs, lexicographers.*

It is known to everyone that the author of the language is the people and definitely it serves the masses. "Word", which is a means of communication and contains a lot of information, is considered the most important element of art and speech. On the other hand, in the language of the heroes of the work and representatives of the language, words appear differently (speech speaks rudely and sharply depending on the level of the listener or the situation). From this point of view, the creator is required to have great skill in conveying the speech of the characters of the work of art. The speech of each character must correspond to the spirituality, behavior, profession, life experience, mentality, age, gender and the speech must mean the personality or show the position of the creator.

It is important to highlight this situation from the point of view of the situation in terms of work of art, then dictionaries are important in the formation of skills for the correct understanding, artistic analysis and interpretation of these works. This prevents the inappropriate use of a word without knowing its true meaning and the creation of stupid sentences. For example, a speaker, who knows that the word "pahan" means "male pig" will never use it instead of the word "father", that is, he will make this word taboo in his speech.

In the given article, the work of Sirojiddin Alikhan Orzu is discussed (1687-1757), a major lexicographer and mature linguist of his time [14; 15]. We analyzed the use of vulgarisms, euphemisms and dysphemism included in the lexicon of limited use as well as some opinions of the author of the dictionary on this matter.

The dictionary explains 2279 words related to various fields, including words used in works of art and popular language. Among them are words that are rude, the meaning of which cannot

be considered as a unit of literary language, and are used in the sense of insults considered contrary to the culture of speech - vulgarisms [1; 203] were also commented on, and the purpose of interpreting these words is to show the need for caution when using these verbal units in speech [1; 203]. In the explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms of Tajik language, vulgarism is defined as follows: Vulgarism (lat. avomcha) rude and coarse words that are not considered a unit of literary language: bashara (in place of the face), freeze (die) instead of), cover the stomach (instead of satiety), as is used, when seeing my eyes (instead of lost). It seems that in the definition of the word vulgarism in Tajik language, synonyms with a negative connotation are also included in the vulgarisms. It is appropriate to combine these words under the term dysphemism and dysphoric words. Of course, vulgar words have a dysphoric meaning.

The author of the dictionary also expressed his opinion on the use of vulgar words, which can be seen in the explanation of the dictionary "tirdon":

Tirdan - sometimes it means a conversation. Fawki guad, verse:

Sukhan tiru dahan chun tirdan ast,

“Sukhan guards and hurries to explain”.

And apparently this is not correct, because Fawki az Rokhi has a joke in part of the song, and part of the poem is incorrect in the dictionary [10; 67] // Tirdan - some say that it means anus. An extraordinary verse:

Words are true, like lips.

The word is dark, urine - an utterance.

Since there are many such words used in satire in the language of fawki and it is incorrect to list such words in the dictionary [10; 67, 152]. The reason for the author's objection in this place is that "tirdon" is not used in a place of worship, but in a crude sense as a joke, and it is indecent to use such vulgar words in speech, even in the form of euphemism.

In fact, this word is a euphemism and it has a dysphemistic character for the mouth, so it is better to taboo such words in speech. It should also be noted that after words acquire a dysphemistic character through migration, they end up in the language, that is, they are adapted to the culture of speech and their use is limited, i.e. euphemisms, no matter how beautiful they are, the subtle, harmless meaning they express, completely forget the essence of the concept given by the taboo cannot eliminate [8; 7].

Certainly, this situation was also emphasized by the author of the dictionary. For example: Sardodan is famous; and Niz Raho is full of snow, especially sardoda tufang and the meaning depends on guza and tirza. This expression means "to let go", "to throw", and it is also used in other meanings, so such words are used in a rude sense, it is advisable not to use it in one place and to follow the requirements of speech culture. Vulgarisms are usually used in fiction in order to "individualize the language of the heroes, create a national and social flavor" to enhance the emotional expressiveness of speech [13; 45] and are used mainly in the speech of the heroes of the work. Writers and poets use such words as widely as possible and try to adhere to the norms of literary speech. They indicate places that are very rude and taboo.

However, in this dictionary that we examined, the image of "everything must be said" is observed, and those parts of a person that are not used in the current books are clearly given, and only in some places the corrupt actions and habits of "verb shane" (bad deed, corrupt work) are mentioned in the style. A. Nurov, a lexicographer, who translated the dictionary "Charogi Hidayat" into the Tajik-Kiril alphabet, adapted some places of use of vulgar words to the requirements of the taboo of modern publishing culture. In vulgarisms, a number of expressions are very clearly visible, such as an extremely negative attitude, discrimination, disdain and insult. Such words live in speech not by their nominative meaning, but by their connotative meaning [4; 60]: “Chutmoroni

- ba mani zani k...de; va in dashnomi akhli Hind ast" // Chutmoroni means a prostitute, adulteress and is an insult to Indians [10; 81]. The obscene words given in "Charogi Hidayat" can be grouped as follows:

Moreover, offensive words: back (carpenter, branch), "canoru manor" (insult) [10; 80], chutmoroni (insult) [10; 81], khoya ba kallaash just, dasti khar (donkey's hand; offensive word) [10; 102], Kunihari [10; 176], lutii (spoiled in Iranian dialect) [10; 189], modarbahato (slander - insult) [10; 190], wrong (antonym of correct; Lucius) [10; 203] sarkun (mufsid - corrupter), rishgov (homtama), guh (human and animal waste) [10; 186]. Sarcasm, saglavand//sagi lavand (sarcasm in the era of the Safavid sultans) Makhdumkurra (actually Kurray Makhdum - Makhdum's foal) [10; 191].

The author notes that the above-mentioned meaning of Lavandi Shokh belongs to the Safavids, in particular, to the era of Shah Abbas II (1602) and in ancient dictionaries it was used mainly in relation to bad behavior women. In fact, this word is "lavender" and shoh is its synonym. This situation is also observed in the dictionary "gichi oshufta", that is, "gichi" is a word and "oshufta" is one of the synonyms of this word. This can be understood from the following example:

Dar Jahon Hamchu man lavender nest,

V-ar buvad yak-du ast chandon nest [10; 189].

Curse: dav nayobad (a curse meaning that he should not see the light, let him lose his strength), murdasho burda (a curse to wish death to the owner through clothes) [10; 193], murdasha shusta (a curse directly related to a person's death wish, i.e. to die and let the gasol wash his body), these two cases are based on a curse, azizmurda (a death wish for one's loved ones, a curse of regional women), khudogir (prone to disasters), namakgir (to show off), nafasshum, mudareg; (low), khanabardosh (stranger), humayoh (poor), batin zan (bad influence).

In fact, despite the fact that these words are vulgar-rude words, they are also euphemic (agho, canoru manor, dasti khar, lavandi shoh, nodurust) and dysphemism.

Modarbahato is a popular term and insult, and modarbahutan is used as a synonym for this word. Truth says:

Thank you for your support.

This happened in Kashmir.

Translation "Thank you for reproaching the Chinese musk",

Although modarbahat is widely used in Kashmir [10; 190].

It is known that colloquial speech is often characterized by vulgarisms. Such lexemes or their vulgar meanings are not considered a unit of literary language, their use is considered contrary to speech culture, but in the language of artistic works such words are used as a methodological tool [1; 203].

According to the dictionary tradition of that time, vulgar words are classified with other words, and examples are taken from works of art. Because comics were very developed at that time. The dictionary notes that such examples are mostly taken from the works of Fawqi and Shifai, comic poets.

There are also cases when things and events are designated not by their names, but by other, more crude words or word combinations. For example, there are known cases when the word "death" or "hellish place" is used in relation to a person, "asphalophilin" is used fluently, and "bojoz" is used for the word "pregnant". Usually, when a word or phrase is used in such a crude sense, it is called dysphemism.

Dysphemism comes from the Greek word "dysphemism", which means "rude expression" and is the opposite of euphemism. Dysphemisms are found in the speech of people with a low

cultural level. In works of art, people with a negative character are usually noticeable in speech [3; 35].

Let us cite the dysphemism given in this dictionary: atashakiy - otashak (sozok), osiy (obstinate), margiy (plague) [10; 194], resmontoza kardan - kafan pora kardan (to recover from illness) [10; 172], nof uftodan (intensification) [10; 204] to lose oneself), davana (to be embarrassed), shikam az aza barovar, shikamro nofi surfa kardan (to cover one's belly, to eat a lot), chakmai mirkhodj (a trifle, a shepherd's fork), khordani zahm va khanjar (to eat a knife, to be wounded), sanduki sir (a mysterious chest), favti davlat (to leave the state, or "to get"), kor gire shudan (dirty work), bodparroni (safsatagoi), halvoi marg (sweet distributed), kirim kushtan (pleasure; to spend time), kushta (to die in one's sleep), guzora (very drunk), gurgoshti (friend), lagati baksht khordan and lagati rozgor horadan (to feel the reaction of fate, regret), makré bar ob dan (to return from the river without water, to shake), magas parondan (to protect a fly, kasod), nargisi dan (to flirt), yak bagal (to hug, a lot), sari har hadi shudan (to find donkey meat, to achieve something trivial), commentary from Khan's "Kashshof" (to speak excessively and presumptuously), bar kase davidan (to rush to the page, to get angry; to embarrass), az nafas andohtan (to inhale, to extinguish, to remain silent), shishaband kardan and shishaki band kardan (to mock), shoks az pusaimoni barovardan (to pull out the branch of regret, to regret), hamyozai chize kashidan (to drag out, desire), harat ba chand (disrespect, not to say who you are), hana bar huro bor kardan (to do destruction), sallohi kardan (to beg, to object), magasroni hinobasta (in fact, this is a device that drives away flies, and is used metaphorically in the meaning of a beard [10; 198], buridan, hana buradan, dastkadji, kogazburi (theft), kafshrubo (thief), sangdog (lover), dry shudan (to remain dry, to be deprived), from sakht khor (to be offended), from zangi kar kardan (to remain silent), from zerhalki khor (to slap), from roydasti khor (to be deceived and to be slapped), roz sang yo az ahan doshtan (shamelessness, ill will), girid sar raftan (to surround), kosa bar sar shikastan (to pass), kor tang giriftan and kor sakht giriftan (to leave weak, tan to leave), mehi chashmi kase budan (to flaunt, to give halal), nahun ba dil dan (to suffer), nazar sekh kardan (to read), tiflro az piston burdan (to wean a child from the breast), dar ovaridan ba vetchin (for fighting), hoki domangir (smelly soil), sarmoshta (cold), alavt (cutthroat, thug), potobapech (conspirator), nimzabon (poor), dahzabani (unproven), morgiri (fat theft), gyurezpo (fugitive)), ris stary doshtan (poverty), sagi royi yakh (kidneys), zanakh zan (disgusting), sagi posakhta (dog with a burnt leg, shame), habbabar (thief), tuhmi haram (born of adultery), pircurgi bagh alzan (extortionist, old wolf), podarkhavo (lie, nonsense, speaking with one's feet from the sky), babai (egoism), kamkosa (stingy), buzbaha (slave), urdakparroni (mockery), ustuhon shikastan (suffering), ashk rehtan (squeezing), tir kashidan (pain), yarfuroshi (praise to a friend), khudkushi (gets excited), sukhani chavida (lie, nonsense), sargozan //sarigovzan (muffet), shuturkhudzhra (unsimilar speech), uzri lang (unacceptable sorry), kabotari duburdzhii (proud), kallapurbadi (proud), gavtazi (praise), mashvarat bo kulokh kardan (advise with a hat, very carefully), yol bastan (pride, arrogance), surno zan (trumpet, beat, cry), ot jovi (chew), ot lip jovi (get angry), ot angushti po (trivial), ot ba ob ron (to deceive), from bos hor (kiss), gul-soz (beautiful, burning the throat), rafta and vorafta (surprised lover).

All nations seem to be forbidden to pronounce the names of certain things and events [3; 36]. In the East, the culture of communication was strongly expressed not only in speech, but also in written sources. The verses of the Koran note that instead of this phenomenon, a "soft" expression (euphemism) is used (that is, the taboo word "ori" (tariz is understood as "to speak, pointing") "in the environment of the culture of communication" [7; 159].

For example: Ohu guzhasht (it's already late) [10; 16] is used in the meaning of a library, a solarium. It should also be noted that in the process of euphemistic expression of some words it

is inappropriate to go overboard, this can be seen in the explanation of Alikhan Orzu to the dictionary "Literature": some misunderstanding contemporaries used *adabgokh* (*madrasah* - J.I.) in the same sense as *understand*, and this is a mistake [10; 19]. The use of another word instead of a word that is inconvenient to pronounce, without a clear indication of the original purpose, these terms expressing the meaning of "dressing up" in speech, is a phenomenon of "euphemisms", that is, the emergence of euphemisms, tradition, soft and eloquent speech is the reason for this [7; 159, 160]. *Tapi ustuhon* eye and ear damage (blindness and deafness), *surkh-surkhbad* disease (hepatitis), *toothache* and the key to *toothache* (attack), *tirdon* [10; 67], *table* [10; 131] *river* [10; 100], *zhalk zanad* [10; 73], *charogkushi* (fornication) [10; 77], *kasae giriftan* (*akhavol giriftan*), a custom of regional Lutians [10; 90], *gulomobora* [10; 156], *rohi kuh raftan* (lat.) [10; 110], *baldness* [10; 129], *halali hostan*, *sar dodan* (to release; to shoot, to grow) [10; 125], *sarpoi* (plural) [10; 130], *sari fatila charb kardan* [10; 129], *junbidan* (*dzimo*), *arrugur* (in the text of D. Bakhriddinov's monograph this word was mistakenly changed to "*arrugaz*", but in the publications "*Naval Kishur*" and "*Dushanbe*" *arrugur* is similar to *kyichuv*, *lie* and *rebellion* are cited) [10; 152], [10; 15], *asoï seharfi* [10; 153], *vomonda* (male genital organ) [10; 214], *kulakh* [10; 173] from *gond* [10; 178], *lust* [10; 207], *nafaskush* (satisfaction of desire) [10; 207], [10; 219], *muhra batas andohtan*, *minor* (executive; in terms of regional masters [10; [10] 201], *medicine* (wine). The above-mentioned words are linguistic taboos expressed through euphemisms, since they are very rude words.

The word "important" is used in two places in the dictionary. As for the regional lutes, these are the carpenter. *Sanadi* is given in as the main word "molmiriya" (an example of a main word). The healer also says:

It is important to be famous and uncontrollable...

It should also be said that in the example of the dictionary "molmiriya" this word is "ba ham sozand" [10; 192]. This word combines slang and euphemism.

Secondly, it is noted that the word has nothing to do with this meaning, and the word "not important" itself also expresses this meaning [10; 219]. Some linguists confuse taboos with words that are not used because they do not adapt to culture. In fact, the fact that some words are not used because they do not adapt to cultural communication is not a taboo. (In our opinion, not using very rude words is also a taboo related to national traditions, religion and morality, especially among Eastern peoples).

However, since it is necessary to refrain from rude, coarse, careless words that do not fit into cultural communication, it is acceptable to choose softer, more pleasant, cultural words and phrases instead. The choice of this word or phrase is one of the manifestations of euphemism. It turns out that there are two sources of euphemisms: 1) taboo; 2) words and phrases that are avoided because they do not fit into the culture.

Besides that, euphemism covers their (taboo and uncultured words - G.I.) meaning due to the derivative meaning of the word or phrase and gives its negative meaning a pleasant, agreeable tone. It should also be said that, as A.J. Omonturdiyev very correctly noted, no matter how beautifully, subtly and harmlessly euphemisms express their meaning, they cannot completely remove from memory the essence of the concept given by the taboo [2; 159]. That is, the negative impression inherited from the expression of the taboo, to a certain extent, retains its traces in the euphemism. This idea is also applicable to euphemisms that replace words and phrases that are not used because they are not included in the cultural chain. After all, no matter how smooth the euphemism is, the negative signs of the inherited meaning inherent in it are preserved to a certain extent [7; 124]. One of the most euphemized concepts in all languages of the world is the concept of death, since this concept is interpreted by all peoples of the world as a terrible, horrible negative

event. Even dysphemization of the concept of death is one of the most observed phenomena in the language. In this dictionary, one can find the following euphemistic and dysphemic words related to "death": az ham guzashtan, joma guzashtan, life supor, guzashtan (to die), hun shudan (to die and be killed), from farman rasi (in the sense of death), kori kasase sokhtan (to kill, to finish the job) [10; 166], heart - from a river broom [104], life - from a broom - the world - from a broom [85]. The following concepts related to death are also given: aspi chobin (coffin), oina peshi nafas doshtan and bar nafas doshtan (state of death), hana ravoz kardan (state of dying), bor bastani zabon (to remain outside the language).

In addition, the dictionary contains many euphemisms accepted in colloquial and artistic speech, where one can observe all cases of the appearance of euphemisms: sabzina (mistress), halal (married woman) [10; 78], peshhimat, peshpafa (employee), sarnashin//sarnishin (master), girid fulun chiz gardam and girid fulunam (to be a victim), uftodagiy (poverty), uftukhez (instability), iqrori shikasta (I made a mistake), umri khud ba kase dodan (the habit of praying, dedicating one's life to someone, becoming a victim), dar hanai fikr raftan (to think), rozi parokanda khordan (a bunch a day), nazokat kardan (to flirt), mijgon ba ham sudan (to flirt), khushi kase burdan and az khush burdani kase (to steal consciousness), ot borik rezi (cunning), ot tawakku hori (to look), safed guftan (in conversation), surkhu zar shudan (shame, embarrassment), sikka ba zar kardan (good ending), surkhu zar shudan (shame, embarrassment), sari zulf doshtan (flirt), shahidboz (angry, liquid), roy dil dodan (compliment), junun kardan (go crazy), gub sweet kardan and shudan (laughter), musk dar shine kardan (drive crazy), shakarob (friend's care), shobosh kardan (to appreciate), gurunadil (mushtaq), labshakar (gloomy), ob ba dasti kase rehtan (service), khalaji kardan (to beat, sift), sarzada raftan (headbutt), safari hob (to snort), gul ba ob afgandan (to start a conspiracy), roy toza doshtan (to be loved), gul ba sari chize zanad (to glorify), mahrami ghor (trusted person - this word arose mainly in connection with our Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) and Abu Bakr Siddiq (ra lib also means close friend) [10; 192] shzanad (to pronounce), shustuhoi khub dodan (to speak roughly; to salt), giriftani dil (to pull).

As we have already mentioned above, even if some of the words found are given as euphemisms, the author clearly mentioned them and explained them descriptively, which means that these words were part of the neutral vocabulary of his time. Synonymous term "penis and sexual organ" instead of "z" became an absolute standard of literary writing and oral speech, including: asoi seharfi (three-letter cane) ki se harf dorad, in the meaning of the instrument consists of three letters. In addition, instead of these words, such euphemisms as "asoi seharfi, chobi seharfi, harfi mardi, nafs, kulah, vomonda, alati mardi, alati tanasul, olat" were used, and the word olat became cultural and is used more in artistic speech, which the author tries to confirm by quoting Zulaikha's address to Yusuf aleihis-salam [10; 16].

It should also be noted that the word "river" is used instead of female genitals. Taking into account the origin of the word "river" among some Turkic peoples, primarily river floods, as well as the name of one of large rivers in Turkish mean female intimate places and it can be assumed that the synonym of this word was adopted as a euphemism. This can also be the reason for the emergence of euphemisms. We can observe this situation when M. Kashgari mentioned in "Devonu lugotit-turk" that the verses of the "Quran" in front of those, who do not know Arabic should be read in a low voice.

Based on the above observations, the following conclusions can be made:

- 1) this dictionary uses many obscene words, most of them are proper words;
- 2) obscene words in the dictionary can be divided into such types as insults, sarcasm, curses, obscene words by gender, found in the speech of women or men;

3) we can observe that rude words, euphemisms and dysphemism used in this dictionary are given in order to “interpret” the events of the use of words in their place in the language according to the requirements of the time. This can be learned from the fact that the author’s preface to the dictionary explains “currently used words, the meaning of which is doubtful and inappropriately used in the language of Persian-speaking Hindustanis and the language of Indians”. An example of this is the use of the positive word "Ago" in Indian language in a negative sense, or the use of the word "Molteni" by the Persians in relation to the Indians and by the Indians in relation to the Mongols, Obi Shiroz is a lexical unit meaning "drinking", this is evident from the meaning of the word haloli khostan, for example, "a terrible crime, lack of culture, to be white in relation to your mother". Of course, knowing the meaning of these words in context helps to avoid stupidity in the use of words, to understand the meaning of the literary text and to criticize the excessive use of vulgar places by poets. The use of these words in speech is taboo and poets are called upon to take the word and creativity seriously.

4) the words used in the dictionary in the form of euphemisms have retained their original crude meaning due to the fact that they contradict the culture of speech, so these words should be tabooed in speech;

5) the dysphemisms explained in the dictionary are mainly taken from the speech or language of the characters, and also reflect the author’s position on the given event.

By summarising it should also be noted that the study of euphemisms and dysphemisms in classical dictionaries is a separate research example, the study of the art of classical texts and the charm of the Persian-Tajik language, which contributed to the replenishment of the world treasury of artistic works with its monuments, and the meaning of the works serves as an important source of understanding. This dictionary contains lexical and phraseological, unambiguous and polysemantic, homonymous and synonymous forms of euphemisms and dysphemisms, which can serve as a reason for a lexicographer to study and highlight these words. The study of euphemistic, dysphemic and vulgar words in classical Tajik language serves to study the lexicographic features of the Persian-Tajik dictionaries and the features of these words in Uzbek linguistics, and also enriches the translation process with sources of lexical units.

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